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3D printing of inorganic-biopolymer composites for bone regeneration

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Abstract

In most cases, bone injuries heal without complications, however, there is an increasing number of instances where bone healing needs major clinical intervention. Available treatment options have severe drawbacks, such as donor site morbidity and limited availability for autografting. Bone graft substitutes containing growth factors would be a viable alternative, however they have been associated with dose-related safety concerns and lack control over spatial architecture to anatomically match bone defect sites. A 3D printing offers a solution to produce patient specific bone graft substitutes that are customized to the patient bone defect with temporal control over the incorporated therapeutics to maximize their efficacy. Inspired by the natural constitution of bone tissue, composites made of inorganic phases, such as nanosilicate particles, calcium phosphate, and bioactive glasses, combined with biopolymer matrices have been investigated as building blocks for the biofabrication of bone constructs. Besides capturing elements of the bone physiological structure, these inorganic/organic composites can be designed for specific cohesivity, rheological and mechanical properties, while both inorganic and organic constituents contribute to the composite bioactivity. This review provides an overview of 3D printed composite biomaterial-inks for bone tissue engineering. Furthermore, key aspects in biomaterial-ink design, 3D printing techniques, and the building blocks for composite biomaterial-inks are summarized.

1. Introduction

1.1. New bone formation

Bone formation arises through a series of simultaneous events that result in the development of the skeleton. During embryogenesis, bone is developed in two evident processes called intramembranous and endochondral ossification. Intramembranous ossification starts with the condensation of mesenchymal populations that differentiate into osteoblasts to directly form bone. Flat bones, such as the skull, maxilla and clavicle, are typically formed by this process. Most bones in the body are formed via endochondral ossification, a mechanism characterized by the formation of bone through a cartilage intermediate. During this process cells in the centre of the mesenchymal condensations evolve into chondrocytes

that secrete the cartilage matrix. Cells adjacent to the chondrocytes form the perichondrium, which establishes the border of the developing skeleton. The cells marking the border withdraw from the cell cycle and undergo hypertrophy, triggering the differentiation of osteoblasts from the perichondrium. The perichondrium is then infiltrated by blood vessels and osteoblasts, changing into the periosteum. The osteoblasts will form the cortical bone around the diaphysis. The hypertrophic cartilage in the diaphysis will start to resorb and osteoblasts progenitors will invade and differentiate into trabecular bone-forming osteoblasts, hematopoietic and endothelial cells create bone marrow, forming the primary ossification centre. The primary ossification centre will expand, and the second ossification centres will develop in one or both ends of the bone. In the

epiphysis, growth plate cartilage is responsible for the longitudinal growth of bones. The growth plates will close with age and eventually be replaced by bone [1, 2].

1.2. Bone healing

Driven by high vascularity and constant turnover, bone has the intrinsic capacity to regenerate tissue function and architecture after injury. The skeleton is a mechanically competent framework that functions as a support for soft tissues, as a lever for muscle actions, protects organs from trauma, it maintains a constant ionic environment in the extracellular fluid via the release of calcium ions, and produces hemopoiesis. In a healthy adult, skeletal homeostasis is regulated by maintaining a fine balance between bone resorption and bone formation, which is mediated by osteoclasts and osteoblasts, respectively [3]. Bone injuries arising from trauma, tumour resection, skeletal abnormalities and infection are common [4] figure 1(a), and in many instances heal spontaneously. Bone healing occurs via two distinct mechanisms, primary and secondary fracture healing [5]. Primary fracture healing occurs in minimal fracture gaps with rigid mechanical stability, and the absence of motion at the fracture site. This healing process occurs sporadically and takes place without callus formation. The most common form of fracture healing is secondary fracture healing, characterized by larger fracture gaps, a less rigid mechanical environment, micromotion at the fracture site and occurs via formation of a callus [6–8]. Secondary fracture healing is a multi-step process, including (a) a fracture hematoma, (b) granulation tissue, (c) a callus, and (d) remodelling, which ultimately leads to new bone formation, figure 1(b) [9–11]. Upon bone injury, a hematoma is formed by blood and immune cells, which initiate a pro-inflammatory response to clear debris, fight infection and initiate healing. After the acute inflammation is resolved, a reparative granuloma tissue is generated, making a template for callus formation [10, 12, 13]. The reparative phase starts with a cartilaginous soft callus, which serves as a template for hard callus formation, and subsequently facilitates the growth of vascular buds into the fracture site. During the latter stages of bone healing, when mineralization takes place, two types of processes can occur, namely endochondral or intramembranous ossification, which will depend on the mechanical stability and type of fracture. Intramembranous ossification, which is connected to primary fracture healing, takes place at the periosteum with precursor cells differentiating into osteoblasts and depositing woven bone. Endochondral ossification, associated with secondary fracture healing, generates new cortical bone via a cartilaginous intermediate tissue [14–16]. In the last phase of bone healing, the remodelling phase, woven bone is replaced with stiffer lamellar bone during a process

mediated by osteoclasts and osteoprogenitor stem cells that differentiate into osteoblasts [7, 15, 17].

1.3. Clinical problems in bone healing

While most bone injuries heal successfully, a proportion of up to 10% or 20% of them will undergo abnormal bone healing [18]. A growing pool of clinical cases due to increased life expectancy and more active lifestyles, coupled with challenging clinical cases, including large defects, tumour resections, skeletal abnormalities and infections, represent an enormous medical challenge. This is further compounded by co-morbidities, such as osteoporosis, diabetes, and immune disorders. Taken together, this increases the number of bone injuries that undergo delayed healing, which might ultimately progress into non-unions. Non-union can be defined as a fracture that has not healed by 9 months and shows no signs of progression upon radiographical examination for 3 months [19]. The main treatment option for large bone defects and clinical gold standard at present is autologous bone grafting, figure 1(c). However, autografts are associated with limitations, including the creation of a secondary injury, and the inherently limited quantity of bone that can be harvested [20]. Bone is the most transplanted tissue after blood and therefore the need for bone graft substitutes is substantial. Alternatives including biomaterials, growth factors, and cell-based therapies have failed to achieve widespread clinical use as reliable bone regenerative solutions, figure 1(c) [21]. Although orthobiologics are promising, the safety profile of growth factor-based therapies, e.g. recombinant-human bone morphogenetic protein-2, has been questioned, mainly due to dose-related side effects [22]. Limitations of orthobiologics include lack of spatial control over scaffold architecture to anatomically match complicated bone defect sites, and a lack of temporal control over the incorporated therapeutics to maximize their efficacy.

1.4. Composite biomaterial-ink as engineered bone graft substitutes

To overcome the limitations of current treatment options, research is increasingly exploiting engineering of 3D printed bone graft substitutes, figure 1(c). A 3D printing enables the fabrication of patient specific bone graft substitutes that are customized to fit the bone defect site. This technology also facilitates control over the microarchitecture of scaffolds, including the pore size, total pore volume, and shape. The pore size in scaffolds should be large enough to facilitate endogenous cell migration, vascular invasion, the deposition of extracellular matrix (ECM), and bone ingrowth, while small enough to support the structural integrity of the construct [23]. Many studies have focused on investigating the effect of scaffold pore sizes on cell infiltration, with a pore size larger than 300–400 μm being reported as promising

[23–26]. Additionally, 3D printing enables the fabrication of heterogeneous inorganic/organic materials to resemble bone composition.

Collagenous proteins account for about 90% of bone organic fraction, together with growth factors, leucine-rich proteoglycans, and non-collagenous proteins, such as osteocalcin, osteonectin, osteopontin, fibronectin, bone sialoprotein II, and BMPs. The inorganic part of bone is predominantly made of hydroxyapatite (HAp) crystals, with phosphate and calcium ions as main building blocks [27]. Given this composite nature of bone, the use of a composite combining inorganic particles in an organic matrix when developing a biomaterial-ink for 3D printing a bone graft substitute is logical.

This review reports insights on the building blocks commonly used to produce composite biomaterial-inks and the relevant 3D printing technologies. Furthermore, recent advances in 3D printed composite scaffolds that have shown promising results in pre-clinical models are emphasized.

2. 3D printing techniques

A 3D printing designates a variety of processes to combine materials and optionally cells according to a pre-defined computer model, thereby significantly expanding the possibility of fabricating constructs with high complexity. The control over the spatial architecture achieved with 3D printing to anatomically match bone defects has huge potential in bone regeneration. In most 3D printing techniques, the structures are fabricated layer-by-layer based on

computer-aided design (CAD) models, which are then translated into a G-code that holds the instructions the motion of the 3 relative axis and the extruder. In order to create patient specific scaffolds, computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging scans can be used to generate a CAD model, from which a patient-specific G-code can be created [28].

To improve the rheological, mechanical, and functional properties of scaffolds for bone regeneration, inorganic fillers have been used in combination with polymers to create bone mimetic bioactive scaffolds [28, 29]. The most common 3D printing techniques used to create these composite scaffolds are extrusion-based printing (EBP), selective laser sintering (SLS), and stereolithography (SLA), figure 2 [28–30].

2.1. Extrusion-based printing (EBP)

EBP is the most popular 3D printing technique to produce scaffolds for bone regeneration, and the most common 3D printing technique in tissue engineering, figure 2(a) [29]. EBP is based on depositing an ink, such as a polymeric solution, melted polymer or hydrogel, through a print-head that is moving in the x - y plane while extruding onto a surface. Extrusion is achieved by applying air or mechanical pressure. The extrusion can be controlled via the amount of pressure applied, the printing speed, the nozzle size, and the temperature, especially for thermoplastic polymers. A disadvantage of EBP is that the resolution achieved by this technique, 50–250 μm , is relatively low compared to other techniques. Significant advantages of EBP are the ease of

use and maintenance, versatility, possibility to customize taking advantage of numerous applications already established, and low cost [30, 31].

2.2. Selective laser sintering (SLS)

In SLS, a laser beam is used to sinter a powder into a 3D object, which is built layer-by-layer with typical resolutions ranging around 20–50 μm , figure 2(b) [32]. The morphology, particle size distribution, and flowability of the used powder are decisive parameters in SLS. Advantages of SLS include its rapid process, large and complex structures that can be produced, and the powder bed that provides support to the building structure, facilitating the fabrication of overhangs in comparison to other 3D printing techniques. This technique uses high temperatures for the sintering, with the disadvantage that it is not possible to incorporate cells and temperature-sensitive biomaterials. Additionally, scaffolds produced using SLS have relatively low mechanical properties, with a rough grainy and porous surface [28, 33].

2.3. Stereolithography (SLA)

SLA is based on a photochemical process where a UV light beam is projected into a liquid photopolymer resin vat curing it layer-by-layer into a 3D object, figure 2(c). Important parameters in SLA are laser

power, scan speed, scan pattern, layer thickness, and resin characteristics [34]. SLA is a relatively quick technique and can produce scaffolds with precise internal architecture and geometries, with resolution in the 50 μm range [35]. Furthermore, SLA enables scaffolds to be fabricated with well-defined porosities, and pore size distribution, interconnectivity and gradients. One disadvantage is that it is intrinsically more expensive than other techniques, and that inorganic fillers may lead to sedimentation in the photopolymer resulting in homogeneity issues affecting the final structure and potentially interfering with the photopolymerization [30, 35, 36].

3. Material building blocks for skeletal bioprinting

The composition of material inks for 3D printing has rapidly evolved during the last decade. The required rigid and mechanically competent structure and, particularly, the need for functional properties of 3D printed implants and skeletal constructs have fostered the rapid growth and development of composite material inks. Biopolymer blends and their combination with inorganic fillers are of great use for biofabrication applications. Taking inspiration from natural bone tissue, inorganic fillers are typically introduced

in biopolymer networks to enhance the mechanical properties, thus providing a tuneable biomaterial-ink system for 3D printing purposes. Additionally, these fillers can be used to modify printability, rheological, and overall functional properties of biomaterial-ink composites used for 3D printing purposes.

Here, a brief list of the biopolymers most commonly combined with inorganic fillers to give composite material inks is provided.

3.1. Natural biopolymers

Natural biopolymers are appealing for their ability to recapitulate the extracellular environment and to encapsulate living cells, which may be embedded into these inks or colonize pre-printed constructs. The mechanical competence of natural biopolymers is often insufficient in load bearing applications, or even to provide appropriate post-printing stability. Further restraints are the limited control over degradation rate, immunogenicity, and batch-to-batch variation [37]. To overcome these restrictions, the addition of other macromolecules and functional additives is desirable.

3.1.1. Alginate

Alginate is among the most popular and widely employed biopolymers. Typically derived from brown algae, this polysaccharide consists of repetitive units of α -L-glucuronic (G) and β -D-mannuronic (M) acids. Their ratio influences physico-chemical properties, such as degradation and swelling ratio of the resulting hydrogel [38]. Thus, M/G ratio and molecular weight can directly influence stiffness, viscosity, shear-thinning and pore-size distribution depending on the concentration of the divalent ions, most often Ca^{2+} , that trigger gel formation [39]. The rapid and simple crosslinking method, coupled with the ease in chemical modification of the polysaccharide chain, make alginate an ideal biopolymer for cell encapsulation, 3D printing and ultimately bone regeneration [40, 41]. Particularly, alginate has been proven effective as a composite biomaterial-ink for 3D printing purposes, as the rheological properties can be tuned due to the inclusion of bioactive inorganic fillers, leading to fine control of the ink shear-thinning and viscoelastic properties [41–43].

3.1.2. Chitosan

Chitosan is derived from deacetylation of chitin, which is the primary component of the exoskeletons of arthropods such as crustaceans. Chitosan is soluble only at pH below 6, and its chemical and physical properties have been modified via functionalization [44]. Chitosan-based biomaterial-inks are increasingly used in skeletal biofabrication approaches as composites, exploiting their suitability to prepare blends with inorganic fillers and nanomaterials [45–47]. Moreover, chitosan's intrinsic

elevated positive charge density is ideal for the inclusion of charged particles, to influence the chitosan printability and viscoelastic properties [48, 49].

3.1.3. Gelatin

Gelatin is derived from collagen via extraction and partial hydrolysis from thermal and chemical processing. While gelatin is water soluble at body temperature, it forms a gel upon cooling to room temperature. The use of gelatin as a cell carrier and ink for skeletal regeneration applications has been widely explored, particularly in combination with chemical modifications. Gelatin derivative with methacryloyl (GelMA) groups is among the most investigated semi-synthetic biopolymer in tissue engineering and biofabrication [50, 51]. In presence of photoinitiators sensitive to UV or visible radiation, GelMA undergoes covalent crosslinking to form a 3D network which unlike gelatin maintains the gel state also at body temperature. Furthermore, GelMA has been extensively used as a versatile vehicle for 3D cell encapsulation and as a biomaterial-ink for bone tissue regeneration over the last decade [52, 53]. The tuneable degree of substitution of photo-crosslinkable groups is of great interest for 3D printing applications as it influences ink stability and degradation post-printing, often being able to match bone regeneration time scale of months [54–56]. Frequently the mechanical properties of gelatin biopolymers are not sufficient to support bone regeneration, and the inclusion of inorganic fillers as reinforcing agents has been explored, gaining encouraging results particularly from 3D printing applications [57].

3.1.4. Gellan gum

Gellan gum is a bacteria-engineered polysaccharide with a temperature-dependent gelation behaviour occurring around 37 °C. Similarly to alginate, the rapid ionic gelation driven by the exposure to divalent ions as well as the ease in chemical modification of the polysaccharide, make the gellan gum a versatile biomaterial-ink for cell encapsulation and 3D printing purposes [58, 59]. The use of gellan gum alone as primary material ink has been rarely found to support mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) viability and functionality [60]. The inclusion of inorganic fillers within the gellan gum network has been proven beneficial for 3D printing and functional purposes, drastically improving the bioactive and functional support of this biomaterial-ink [61].

3.1.5. ECM-based materials

Decellularized ECM (dECM) materials have recently come to the fore as crucial building blocks for the engineering of functional and bioactive biomaterial-inks. However, the elevated batch-to-batch variability, the rare availability of tissue sources and the poor mechanical properties have limited the printability of

ECM-based inks [62, 63]. Nevertheless, recent studies have investigated the simple, yet effective, modification of ECM-based inks using inorganic fillers to ameliorate printability and ultimate functionality post-printing [64].

3.2. Synthetic polymers

Compared to naturally derived biopolymers, their synthetic counterparts are usually chemically better defined, are available in numerous structures and variations, their properties can be fine-tuned, and overall display higher consistency and lower batch-to-batch variation. Typically, synthetic biopolymers display limited cell attachment and biological activity, although chemical derivatization can add these functionalities to guide cell response and drive tissue regeneration. Driven by the increasing amount of research in biomedical 3D printing, the use of synthetic biopolymers as primary carriers for inorganic fillers has also expanded. The control over the rheological properties of engineered synthetic biopolymers provides a platform for the inclusion of bioactive inorganic fillers that might aid the enhancement in functional response of the 3D printed synthetic inks upon implantation.

3.2.1. Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG)

PEG is among the most used synthetic biopolymers for biomedical applications. This polymer is characterized by a markedly hydrophilic nature, versatile chemistry for producing linear, branched or dendrimeric structures with controlled molecular weight and end functional groups. Therefore, PEGs can cover a wide range of properties such as elasticity, mouldability, degradation rate and chemistry of network formation. PEG has been widely used in 3D printing applications for more than a decade is becoming an increasingly popular ink [65, 66], selected to standardize biomaterial-ink printability and shape fidelity [67].

PEG diacrylate is a popular PEG derivative that allows the use of photo-initiators to generate irreversible bonds essential to reinforce the ultimate 3D printed structure. PEG has been combined with inorganic fillers for adapting its properties towards bone tissue regeneration, including the Young's moduli, viscoelastic and shear-thinning behaviour [68, 69].

3.2.2. Poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA)

PLLA is a popular biodegradable thermoplastic polymer for applications in medicine and beyond. PLLA synthesis is well established for a range of mechanical properties, and its degradation to lactate, which is an ubiquitous metabolite, has been widely investigated, conferring wide popularity to the use of PLLA in the medical field as base material for bioresorbable stitches, screws and implants [70, 71]. Due to the relatively low cost and a melting temperature of 150 °C,

compatible with many benchtop printers, PLLA has been widely used for the fabrication of 3D scaffolds via EBP for tissue engineering purposes [72].

Limitations of PLLA include suboptimal thermal stability, elevated brittleness and lower mechanical properties compared to other polymers that can be processed via EBP. PLLA reinforcement with fibres and nanofillers has also been widely investigated as well as its chemical modification [73].

Since it can be synthesized from renewable sources, for example corn, PLLA is currently being investigated in the context of green chemistry and circular chemistry [74].

3.2.3. Poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA)

PLGA is a synthetic co-polymer of poly(lactic acid) and poly(glycolic acid) (PLA and PGA) employed in numerous devices approved for clinical use by the food and drug administration (FDA) and its equivalent in other geographical areas. The specific ratio of PLA and PGA can be used to influence the degradation rate and the mechanical properties. Biocompatibility, tuneable mechanical properties and low melting point (120 °C) make PLGA an ideal material for numerous 3D tissue printing applications, such as bone and cartilage. Similarly to PLLA, thermal instability and the risk of formation of toxic by-products at high temperature due to unprocessed solvent entrapment, limit the use of this co-polymer in EBP [75, 76]. Thus, organic solvents, like acetone and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), can be employed to solubilize PLGA [77]. A number of fillers and additives have been added to the PLGA co-polymer tuning degradation, mechanical properties and biological activity [78].

3.2.4. Polycaprolactone (PCL)

PCL is an aliphatic polyester employed in numerous devices cleared by the appointed authorities. PCL is mostly hydrophobic, however its biodegradation rate can be tuned by the inclusion of inorganic fillers and additives, aiming to match specific skeletal regeneration rates. PCL, due to the low melting temperature (60 °C), is extremely popular as 3D printable biopolymer as it can be processed by numerous technologies for the fabrication of complex scaffolds such as electrospinning, melt-electrowriting (MEW) and fused deposition modelling [79–83]. This has found core applications as unique support technology for bone biofabrication. PCL deposition has been explored in close combination with cell-laden hydrogel printing for the fabrication of hybrid, cell-laden and acellular, scaffold fabrication in bone regeneration. While PCL hydrophobicity and limited biological activity might be a limitation for bone repair, its combinations with inorganic fillers have been exploited to augment PCL mechanical properties, tune the degradation rate and biocompatibility properties

thereby opening further opportunities for bone tissue engineering [84–87].

3.3. Inorganic fillers

Inorganic fillers have been demonstrated to be highly bioactive and capable of enhancing bone formation and regeneration [88, 89]. The presence of elements found within the mineral matrix of natural bone, such as calcium, phosphorus and silicon as major components, grants inorganic materials used for bone regeneration the ability to integrate with skeletal tissues and support the healing process. Calcium is naturally entrapped by sulphated glycosaminoglycans within the healthy bone tissue and it is functional for bone formation and regeneration. Active osteoblasts secrete enzymes, like alkaline phosphatase (ALP), that degrade the deposited ECM, modulating the release of calcium and phosphate ions, forming HAp crystals, regulating bone remodeling and bone homeostasis [90–92]. Particularly, early studies showed the essential role that silicon plays in the human diet and physiological functioning, highlighting the pivotal role for bone growth, development and structural integrity [93–95].

A plethora of inorganic fillers is yet to be fully explored for 3D bone bioprinting purposes. While holding intrinsic attractive biological properties such as antimicrobial and angiogenic abilities, other inorganic particles such as mineral oxide compounds have been used in combination with printable biopolymers. Particularly, magnesium (MgO) [96], zinc (ZnO) [97] and graphene oxide [98, 99] have been reported for inclusion in printable inks as functional nanofillers holding promising results towards skeletal regeneration.

3.3.1. Nanosilicate particles (NSPs)

NSPs biomaterials have been proven highly stimulatory for differentiation towards the bone lineage, thus their use in 3D printing approaches is growing apace with the study of their (potential) osteoinductive properties [100].

Clay NSPs are sheet-silicates made of inorganic layered nanomaterials, structured as tetrahedral and octahedral sheets. Among the most studied, Laponite® is a smectite particularly appealing for its ability to interact with polymers and the modification of rheological properties upon dispersion in ion-free water [101, 102]. The particle size, 25–30 nm diameter and 1 nm thickness [103], the anisotropic surface charge, positive rim and negative surface [100], and the cation exchange capacity, 80–150 meq/100 g [104], are major properties of interest for scientists looking to engineer new active and functional biomaterials for bone regeneration. Laponite® nanoparticles have been particularly used in bone tissue engineering as they are able to retain compounds of interest and degrade into non-toxic by-products and

ions capable of supporting bone differentiation and growth [100, 104].

3.3.2. Calcium phosphate (CaP)

Given the similarity to the natural bone mineral phase, the use of CaP-based materials for the fabrication of bone graft substitutes is appealing. The first attempts to use CaP for bone repair date back more than a century ago [105]. Early developments of CaP-based materials were sustained by the urgent need for synthetic alternatives to bone grafts, due to the scarcity of viable tissue substitutes and the invasiveness of the bone harvesting procedure in autografts.

HAp ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) is the major component of the inorganic phase of bone tissue, with a specific Ca/P ratio of 1.67 [106]. However, HAp is usually present as a calcium-deficient apatite, as the traces of phosphate groups (PO_4) and other impurities can alter the Ca/P ratio. Seminal studies have reported the synthesis of HAp for the repair of dental and skeletal defects [107, 108]. Since the 1980s, synthetic alternatives to natural HAp have been largely exploited for the augmentation of bone, filling and coating of skeletal implants. The particulate form of HAp has been used as inorganic filler for biomaterial-inks for hard tissue regeneration and, more recently, for 3D printing purposes [109]. The inclusion of specific concentration, form and composition of HAp particles allow for the modification of rheological, mechanical and, more importantly, bioactive properties of the 3D printed composite scaffolds [109, 110].

Tricalcium phosphate (TCP) ($\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$) materials have been first exploited by Albee in 1920 observing the successful repair of fractures [105]. In particular, beta-TCP (β -TCP) has been proven pre-clinically functional for *in vivo* bone regeneration when used as filling granules [111] or bulk scaffolds [112]. These CaP-based materials have emerged as promising bioactive inorganic fillers for biomaterial-inks for skeletal biofabrication purposes due to the osteoconductivity or even osteoinductivity, although this property is still debated [113]. The formidable biocompatibility and bioactivity of β -TCP, as well as the positive results for material functionality *in vivo*, make β -TCP particularly interesting for clinical applications [114]. The possibility to blend HAp with β -TCP at different ratios varying its properties, has been exploited generating a series of composite biphasic CaPs, with significant increase in compressive strength, up to 1.7 MPa, compared to HAp-free β -TCP constructs [115].

3.3.3. Bioactive glasses (BAGs)

BAGs date back more than five decades when Hench *et al* reported for the first time a class of materials able to release ionic components, such as Si, Ca, P and Na, that were found active for the induction of bone formation and repair [116]. The 45S5 Henchglass® has found over the years numerous applications in

tissue engineering, specifically in bone regeneration. The silicate backbone contains 55%–60% wt SiO₂ and can be modified with Na₂O, CaO and P₂O₅ at different ratios, including elements such as strontium and zinc [117, 118].

BAG binds to hard and soft tissue, and specifically to bone. The degradation kinetic of BAG is of pivotal interest for bone healing. A chemical reaction occurs at the interface between the glass and skeletal tissue where ions are exchanged and calcium-deficient carbonated apatite is deposited, while skeletal cells are able to migrate, preferentially towards BAG surface, proliferate and differentiate towards bone lineage. Multiple studies, reported in detailed reviews elsewhere [119, 120], have confirmed the ability of BAG to actively stimulate and direct osteoblasts proliferation and stem cell differentiation, upregulating a number of genes that are involved in bone formation.

4. 3D printing of composite inorganic-biopolymer inks for bone regeneration

The combination of biopolymers and inorganic fillers has been proven successful for bone tissue engineering approaches, particularly for strategies using 3D printing. The inorganic fillers can support the 3D printing of soft materials by tuning the rheological properties and at the same time providing functional mineralization nuclei for the deposition of new bone. Here, different approaches that have been explored for 3D printing composite inks for bone regeneration are summarized and are sub-categorized into three major inorganic fillers: (a) NSPs, (b) CaP, and (c) BAG, table 1.

4.1. Composites with NSPs

The inclusion of NSPs such as nanoclay into biopolymers has been widely explored in bioprinting in recent years. NSPs hold the ability to modify the rheological properties of most biopolymers, drastically altering the shear thinning, loss and storage moduli following 3D deposition, as shown in figure 3(a). In this section, approaches using 3D printable composite inks with NSPs for bone regeneration are illustrated.

Laponite® is a popular NSPs and has been widely investigated in this field. It was combined with gellan gum to create a 3D printable ink that was shown to be stable *in vitro*, had limited swelling, and demonstrated retention capabilities with the absence of burst release [61]. Cell-laden constructs with C2C12 were allowed to proliferate for over 21 d and when loaded with vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and implanted in a 10 day-old developing chick chorioallantoic membrane (CAM), extensive vasculature infiltration could be observed. This work demonstrates that growth factors can add biological function to inorganic-biopolymer composites. Similarly,

Laponite®, GelMA and VEGF were combined in a composite ink for human MSCs (hMSCs) encapsulation, enabling 3D bioprinting of functional cell-instructive constructs with controlled drug release [57]. The composite ink showed enhanced shape fidelity, interconnected pores, and no significant changes in cell viability over 21 d. This study showed also that the scaffolds supported osteogenic differentiation of hMSCs, and when implanted in a CAM assay demonstrated integration and vascularization. In both cited examples, the presence of charged nanoclay in the composites was key to achieve precise control over VEGF release, preventing the burst release of the growth factor and fostering the retention and prolonged stimulation of the host system.

Ahlfeld *et al* engineered a blend of Laponite® and alginate-methylcellulose for the 3D delivery of immortalized hMSCs [121]. In this study, it was shown that the combination with a biopolymer enabled 3D bioprinting of hMSCs that maintained viability over 21 d. These printed structures stayed cohesive during extended culture periods and showed promising results as drug delivery platform for bovine serum albumin as a model and, VEGF due to a more sustained release profile. In a follow-on work, a similar combination of Laponite® and alginate-methylcellulose allowed for hMSC encapsulation sustaining viability for up to 3 weeks, and 3D bioprinting [42]. Scaffolds were loaded with VEGF, seeded with human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs), and tested in a CAM assay, resulting in integration and *ex vivo* vascularization. When the scaffolds were loaded with bone morphogenetic protein (BMP)-2 and subcutaneously implanted in athymic nude mice, there was extensive mineralization after 8 weeks and 3D printed cell-laden structures showed significantly more bone formation compared to acellular and casted scaffolds. The synergistic effect of growth factors and cells retained within the 3D printed constructs was possible thanks to the inclusion of a specific concentration of nanoclay suspension, granting the control over vasculature and bone formation *in vivo*.

Recently, Lee *et al* harnessed the combination of cationic silica nanoparticles of size below 100 nm and anionic polymer alginate and gellan, engineering a novel nanocomposite ink that showed high printing fidelity, limited swelling and enhanced mechanical properties [122]. Interestingly, nanoparticles larger than 100 nm did not enhance the storage moduli, proving that the molecular properties of the need to be carefully matched with those of the polymer network, and providing enough surface area to support the electrostatic interaction. Moreover, Lee *et al* 3D printed chondrocytes using this novel nanocomposite ink, which were found viable and able to proliferate over 21 d.

Inorganic fillers were employed also in combination with natural biopolymers by Jeon *et al* whom reported 3D printed composite scaffolds of silanated

Table 1. Highlighted studies reporting 3D printing of composite inorganic-biopolymer inks for bone regeneration.

	Inorganic filler	Biopolymer	3D printing technique	Particle size	Pore size	Biological test model	References
Nanosilicate particles (NSPs)	Laponite®	Gellan gum	EBP	—	1.8 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : C2C12 cells <i>Ex vivo</i> : CAM	[61]
	Laponite®	GelMA	EBP	25 nm	—	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs <i>Ex vivo</i> : CAM	[57]
	Laponite®	Alginate-methylcellulose	EBP	—	2 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[121]
	Laponite®	Alginate-methylcellulose	EBP	—	—	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs, HUVECs <i>Ex vivo</i> : CAM <i>In vivo</i> : subcutaneous athymic nude mice	[42]
Cationic silica nanoparticles Silane modified silica particles HAp + β -TCP + CaSiO ₃	—	Alginate/gellan	EBP	41 nm	—	<i>In vitro</i> : chondrocytes	[122]
	—	PCL	EBP	800 nm	500 μ m	<i>In vitro</i> : MG-63 cells	[123]
	—	Distilled water + glycerol + ammonium polyacrylate, hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose	EBP	—	250 μ m	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs <i>In vivo</i> : subcutaneous skull rats	[124]
	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Calcium phosphate (CaP)	α -TCP + nanoHAp	PCL	EBP	3.83 μ m + <200 nm	500 μ m	<i>Ex vivo</i> : osteochondral constructs	[125]
	Hap	Alginate	EBP	—	400 \times 400 μ m	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs <i>In vivo</i> : male Sprague-Dawley rats	[126]
	β -TCP	Alginate-GelMA	EBP	14 μ m	—	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[113]
	α -TCP	NaHPO ₄ , glycerol, polyoxyethylenesorbitan monooleate	EBP	1.34–6.19 μ m	500 \times 1500 \times 250 μ m	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[129]
	CPC	Plasma (from human whole blood), alginate, methylcellulose	EBP	—	0.5 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[127]
	Hap	PTMC	SLA	—	750–800 μ m	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[130]
	Hap	PTMC	SLA	—	720 μ m	<i>In vivo</i> : calvarial defect rabbit	[131]
	β -TCP	Collagen I	EBP	—	—	<i>In vivo</i> : orbital floor defect sheep	[133]
	BCP	Alginate	EBP	106–212 μ m	3 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : hASCs, MC3T3-E1 preosteoblasts <i>In vitro</i> : MG-63 cells	[128]

(Continued.)

Table 1. (Continued.)

Inorganic filler	Biopolymer	3D printing technique	Particle size	Pore size	Biological test model	References
β -TCP + nanoHAp	PTMC	SLA	—	720 μm	<i>In vivo</i> : subcutaneous female nude mice <i>In vitro</i> : K7M2 osteoblasts <i>In vivo</i> : critical size bone defect tibia and cranium rabbit	[132]
nanoHAp	PCL	SLS	150 \times 20 nm	1 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[137]
Hap	PCL, PLGA	EBP	20–30 μm	300 μm	<i>In vivo</i> : femur defect rabbit <i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs <i>In vivo</i> : subcutaneous mouse, posterolateral spinal fusion rat, primate calvarial defect	[86]
β -TCP + HAp + Bio-Oss + bone dECM	PCL	EBP	20–50 μm	>500 000 μm^2	<i>In vitro</i> : ASCs	[134]
Hap	Starch, PCL	EBP	—	—	<i>In vitro</i> : hFOB 1.19 osteoblasts	[135]
Magnesium-substituted- β -TCP + carbonated HAp + BCP	PPF	SLA	—	353–429 μm	<i>In vivo</i> : critical sized calvarial defect rabbit	[141]
nanoHAp	PPF	SLA	550 nm	430 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts	[142]
Amorphous CaP (molar ratio Ca:P 1.5)	PHBV	SLS	10–30 nm	2 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : C3H10T1/2 MSCs	[138]
CaP + carbonated HAp	PLLA + PHBV	SLS	10–30 nm	0.8 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : SaOS-2 cells	[139]
Hap	PLGA	EBP	200 \times 50 nm	350 \times 350 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MSCs, ASCs <i>In vivo</i> : subcutaneous mice	[143]
β -TCP	PCL	SLS	—	300–500 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : porcine ASCs <i>In vivo</i> : nude mice	[140]
Amorphous CaP + GSH	Alginate + cellulose	EBP	110 μm	298–377 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts	[144]
Bioactive glasses (BAGs)	Orthophosphoric acid, pyrophosphoric acid, isopropanol	EBP	18–92 μm	—	—	[145]
Polyphosphate (molar ratio SiO ₂ :CaO:P ₂ O ₅ of 55:40:5)	Alginate + gelatin	EBP	55 nm	—	<i>In vitro</i> : SaOS-2 cells	[146]
80% SiO ₂ , 16% CaO and 4% P ₂ O ₅	Sodium alginate + gelatin	EBP	74 μm	400–600 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MG-63 cells	[157]

(Continued.)

Table 1. (Continued.)

Inorganic filler	Biopolymer	3D printing technique	Particle size	Pore size	Biological test model	References
Mol% 47.12 SiO ₂ , 6.73 B ₂ O ₃ , 6.77 CaO, 22.66 Na ₂ O, 1.72 P ₂ O ₅ , 5 MgO, 10 SrO	Gelatin + alginate	EBP	13–5 μm	0.55–0.60 mm	<i>In vitro</i> : SaOS-2 cells, hMSCs	[147]
Molar ratio Si:P:Ca of 80:5:15 with Ca substituted by Zn	Alginate + methylcellulose	EBP	45 μm	—	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[148]
2.8 g Ca(NO ₃) ₂ · 4H ₂ O, 1.46 g TEOP, 13.4 g TEOS, 8 g P123	PCL	EBP	—	6.66 nm	<i>In vitro</i> : C3H10T1/2	[159]
Mesoporous silica-calcia nanoparticles (mol% 70 SiO ₂ and 30 CaO)	Alginate dialdehyde-gelatin	EBP	120 nm	415 μm	<i>In vivo</i> : subcutaneous nude mice <i>In vitro</i> : MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts	[158]
45S5 BAG (wt% 45 SiO ₂ , 24.5 CaO, 24.5 Na ₂ O, 6 P ₂ O ₅)	PLA	EBP	4 μm	750 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts, hASCs	[151]
Li-BAG (molar ratio Li:Ca:P:Si of 5:10:5:80)	PLGA	EBP	—	330 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MSCs <i>In vivo</i> : calvarial defect diabetes mellitus mice	[160]
45S5 BAG (wt% 45 SiO ₂ , 24.5 CaO, 24.5 Na ₂ O, 6 P ₂ O ₅)	PHBV	EBP	5 μm	100–800 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : NIH/3T3, MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts, MSCs	[152]
Mol% 55 SiO ₂ , 40 CaO, 5 P ₂ O ₅	Alginate dialdehyde-gelatin	EBP	40–100 nm	—	<i>In vitro</i> : MG-63 cells	[149]
Amine-functionalized copper-doped mesoporous BAG nanoparticles	Alginate dialdehyde-gelatin	EBP	191 nm	692 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MG-63 cells, ST2 cells, mouse MSCs, HUVECs	[150]
SGCMs	PLA	EBP	1–15 μm	337 × 500 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[153]
BAG 13–93 (wt% 53 SiO ₂ , 6 Na ₂ O, 12 K ₂ O, 5 MgO, 20 CaO, 4 P ₂ O ₅) + HAp	Alginate	EBP	34 × 72 μm	—	<i>In vitro</i> : MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts	[154]
S53P4 BAG (53% SiO ₂ , 23% Na ₂ O, 20% CaO, 4% P ₂ O ₅)	PLA	EBP	25–42 μm	200 × 2000 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : hMSCs	[155]
Niobium containing BAG (wt% 45 SiO ₂ , 24 CaO, 24 Na ₂ O, 6 P ₂ O ₅ , 1 Nb ₂ O ₅)	PBAT	EBP	4.56 μm	400 μm	<i>In vitro</i> : MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts <i>In vivo</i> : rat femur	[156]

ASCs: adipose derived stem cells; **BCP**: biphasic calcium phosphate; **CAM**: chick chorioallantoic membrane; **CaP**: calcium phosphate; **CPC**: calcium phosphate cement; **CSH**: calcium sulfate hemihydrate; **deCM**: decellularized extracellular matrix; **EBP**: extrusion based printing; **GelMA**: gelatin-methacryloyl; **HAp**: hydroxyapatite; **hMSCs**: human mesenchymal stem cells; **HUVECs**: human umbilical vein endothelial cells; **nanoHAp**: nano hydroxyapatite; **PBAT**: poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate); **PCL**: polycaprolactone; **PHBV**: poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate); **PLA**: polylactic acid; **PLGA**: poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid); **PLLA**: poly-L-lactic acid; **PPF**: poly(propylene fumarate); **SGCMs**: spray dried glass-ceramic microparticles; **SLA**: stereolithography; **SLS**: selective laser sintering; **β-TCP**: β-tricalcium phosphate.

silica particles and PCL [123]. The addition of the inorganic filler increased the mechanical properties in comparison to the PCL alone. Upon *in vitro* testing, the composite performed better than PCL alone, showing higher proliferation rate and mineralization of MG-63 cells.

In a study performed by Liu *et al* HAp together with β -TCP and $CaSiO_3$ were combined with a mixture of distilled water, glycerol, ammonium polyacrylate, and hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose [124]. This composite ink enabled 3D printing of hierarchical structures with interconnected pores that enhanced *in vitro* cell adhesion, stimulation of hMSCs differentiation and HUVEC gene expression. *In vivo* studies were carried out in an ectopic model of subcutaneous site on the skull of rats, resulting in capillary formation, bone augmentation and new bone matrix formation, revealing a promising strategy for bone regeneration. Overall, results demonstrate that the addition of NSPs to natural and synthetic polymers widens the range of chemical, mechanical and biological properties achievable.

4.2. Composites with CaP

CaP is the main component of the inorganic part of bone contributing to its mechanical and biological properties, hence CaP-based composites have been extensively investigated for bone repair applications and for the engineering of 3D bioprinted skeletal implants, figure 3(b). This section collects a selection of studies investigating CaP particles in 3D printed composites with an organic matrix.

Diloksumpan *et al* reported the combination of multi-material 3D printing using reinforced

hydrogel-ceramic interfaces consisting of α -TCP and nanoHAp together with PCL [125]. The complex but elegant use of EBP and MEW allowed for the fabrication of implantable osteochondral constructs. The 3D printed implants were fabricated starting from a PCL microfiber mesh produced via MEW, where a CaP paste was deposited via EBP. Following the fabrication of the rigid portion of the construct, a soft hydrogel was then placed on top to integrate with the chondral compartment. Thus, the mechanical properties of the cartilage, bone and interfacial zone could be controlled by the spatial arrangement and architecture of MEW mesh and 3D printed ceramic fibres. Although the overall approach might be regarded as relatively sophisticated, the functional results obtained in this study demonstrate the potential of combining different biofabrication technologies with inorganic material applications for bone regeneration.

CaP can function as a reservoir of Ca^{2+} ions, which can be exploited for the ionic crosslinking of alginate, and this combination has been employed in several studies. Chang *et al* used arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (RGD)-functionalized alginate scaffolds paired with a rigid printed HAp structure [126]. The produced scaffolds had an osteoid-like stiffness and showed improved hMSC viability, migration and osteogenic differentiation. *In vivo* implantation of the constructs in male Sprague-Dawley rats facilitated collagen synthesis, angiogenesis, osteogenesis, and induced bone formation, revealing a promising strategy for bone regeneration. Kosik-Kozioł *et al* engineered a functional approach to 3D print β -TCP dispersed in an alginate-GelMA ink solution [113].

The modular printing platform allowed the patterning of β -TCP particles, granting the precise spatial distribution in 3D, localizing a β -TCP-free (cartilage) and a β -TCP-rich (bone) portion of the printed scaffold. Exploiting the mechanism leading to the mineralization of cartilaginous tissue, in this study a novel technology was unravelled for the fabrication of osteochondral tissue on demand. In another report by Ahlfeld *et al*, a mixture of a CaP cement (CPC) paste with plasma from human whole blood, alginate, and methylcellulose was used for the bioprinting of hMSCs [127]. Constructs with high spatial accuracy and open porosity could be plotted, and hMSCs showed spreading and proliferation within the bioink. In a model from Loozen *et al*, a composite ink was combined with non-viral gene therapy [128]. In this study, inorganic filler biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP) together with the biopolymer alginate was combined to deliver a slow constant level of BMP-2. A 3D printed constructs were accurate and reproducible in shape, size, and pore geometry, which allowed diffusion and blood vessel ingrowth. Cells were successfully transfected with the plasmid DNA encoding BMP-2 and were differentiated into the osteogenic lineage, confirmed by increased production of BMP-2 and ALP. *In vitro* experiments in this study also showed that porous structures increased BMP-2 production in the first week more than solid constructs. However, subcutaneous implantation in female nude mice did not result in bone formation.

Printing with a water-based support solution is not limited to alginate, and it was used also by Romanazzo *et al* for patterning a skeletal structure within a cell-laden bath via omnidirectional printing, by harnessing the curing properties of an α -TCP ink [129]. Here, complex 3D constructs able to recapitulate the *in vivo* skeletal microenvironment were generated. Thanks to dissolution and re-precipitation, α -TCP promotes controlled growth of nanocrystals via HAp nucleation, due to the rapid hydrolysis of the printed ink. The cells within the support bath were found viable after several weeks of culture and hMSCs differentiated towards osteoblasts when in proximity of the printed implant. This novel approach holds great potential for further development and application for bone tissue engineering.

In a study performed by Guillaume *et al*, a composite ink that combines HAp and poly(trimethylene carbonate) (PTMC) was used in a SLA 3D printing process to produce scaffolds with controlled macro-architecture [130]. Incorporation of HAp was key to improve hMSC osteogenic differentiation *in vitro* and bone healing *in vivo* in a rabbit calvarial defect. In a further study from the same group, scaffolds fabricated using SLA with PTMC and HAp were implanted in orbital floor defects in sheep [131]. Results demonstrated a rapid neovascularization and bone formation after 4 weeks, without the addition of biotherapeutics such as BMPs. Another example of PTMC

was reported by Teotia *et al*, studying the impact of a functionalized 3D printed composite scaffolds on bone regeneration in critical size bone defects in rabbits [132]. Here, β -TCP and nanoHAp were combined with PTMC and the obtained composite ink was functionalized with a controlled release of BMP-2 and zoledronic acid. To create higher porosity for enhanced cell infiltration, scaffolds were filled with a microporous cryogel. *In vivo* experiments with the scaffold implanted in a critical size defect in tibia and cranium of a rabbit resulted in a conductive surface inducing bone formation and improved healing in both the tibia and cranium defect.

Kim and Kim showed successful inclusion of MC3T3-E1 preosteoblasts and human adipose stem cells (hASCs) into a composite ink of β -TCP and type I collagen [133]. Here, a mechanically stable porous cell-laden construct was fabricated, and cells in the ink stayed viable and proliferated. Cells in the composite scaffolds showed significantly higher osteogenic activities compared to pure type I collagen, indicating that β -TCP served as an osteogenic trigger. Although collagen is the biopolymeric component mainly contributing to bone mechanical and biological properties, there is a limited number of studies investigating its combination with CaP or other inorganic components for 3D printing of bone constructs. This might be due fact that collagen forms slurries with suboptimal printability properties.

On the contrary, PCL, alone or in composites, has been widely investigated in EBP, mainly due to its melting point of around 60 °C facilitating processing.

In a study published by Nyberg *et al*, a porous PCL scaffold was printed and functionalized with TCP, HAp, Bio-Oss, or bone dECM [134]. Osteoinduction of different formulations was assessed *in vitro* using ASCs, showing that mineralization was increased for all formulations compared to PCL alone. Koski *et al* showed a composite ink composed of HAp, binder starch and PCL [135]. The addition of starch in the composite ink improved the mechanical properties and biocompatibility of osteoblasts. Jakus *et al* reported a composite of HAp with PCL or PLGA, which exhibited elastic mechanical properties, porosity, and where cells were viable and proliferating. The properties of hyperelastic PLGA scaffolds have already been explored and described before, showing high internal porosity, elastic properties, and ability to support cell proliferation [136]. *In vitro* evaluation showed osteogenic differentiation of hMSCs, while *in vivo* studies subcutaneous in mice, posterolateral spinal fusion in rats, and primate calvarial defect resulted in no adverse immune response, vascularization, integration, while leading to new bone formation. According to the authors, this biomaterial composite is highly versatile, osteoregenerative, scalable and surgically friendly [86].

Besides EBP and MEW, SLS has also been employed for 3D printing of PCL-based constructs

for bone regeneration. In a paper from Xia *et al* nanoHAp and PCL were combined to fabricate scaffolds using SLS [137]. The produced scaffolds exhibited pre-designed, well-ordered macropores and interconnected micropores. Further, when the constructs were cultured *in vitro* with hMSCs, cells were viable and proliferating up to 28 d. *In vitro* osteogenesis showed that in PCL scaffolds containing nanoHAp the mineralization, ALP activity and Alizarin Red S staining were increased compared to pure PCL scaffolds. This was also confirmed *in vivo* in femur defects of rabbits, with enhanced new bone formation and good biocompatibility. SLS was also used by Duan and Wang for producing nanocomposite scaffolds with customized architecture, controlled porosity, and interconnected pores using nanocomposite microspheres based on amorphous CaP and poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) [138]. Scaffolds were modified with gelatin, heparin and a controlled release of BMP-2, enhancing ALP activity and osteogenic differentiation of C3H10T1/2 MSCs. In another study from Duan *et al* nanocomposite microspheres made of carbonated HAp combined with PHBV or PLLA were developed, again using SLS [139]. Scaffolds showed controlled microstructure and interconnected pores. *In vitro* evaluation of SaOS-2 cells cultured in combination with the scaffolds resulted in high viability, while the addition of carbonated HAp significantly increased cell proliferation and ALP activity for the scaffolds consisting of PHBV and carbonated HAp compared to the PLLA and PHBV alone and PLLA together with carbonated HAp. Liao *et al* developed 3D printed scaffolds via SLS using β -TCP and PCL to enhance osteogenesis [140]. Fabricated scaffolds were coated with type I collagen after 3D printing. The addition of β -TCP into PCL increased the compressive modulus. *In vitro* studies of porcine ASCs demonstrated best osteogenic differentiation when cultured on top of the composite scaffold. Furthermore, scaffolds were implanted *in vivo* in nude mice with the outcome that the composite scaffold showed more woven bone and vascularization.

Another popular printing technique is SLA. Research performed by Dadsetan *et al* shows fabrication of scaffolds using SLA with poly(propylene fumarate) (PPF) and coated with magnesium-substituted- β -TCP, carbonated HAp, or BCP and loaded with BMP-2 with controlled release for functional restoration of large bone defects [141]. *In vivo* implantation in critical sized calvarial defects in rabbits, resulted in new bone formation for all scaffolds, osteointegration and osteoconductivity, suggesting a synergistic effect between CaP and BMP-2 delivery. Lee *et al* used SLA to develop scaffolds consisting of HAp and PPF for bone regeneration [142]. Fabricated scaffolds had connected pores and the HAp created nano/microscale morphology. Additionally, *in vitro* tests were performed using MC3T3-E1 cells and cell

adhesion and proliferation was improved upon HAp inclusion.

More recently, Babilotte *et al* have demonstrated the blending of HAp and PLGA, to synthesize a printable material via EBP deposition. The loading of either 5% or 10% (w/w) HAp was confirmed homogeneous without significantly impairing printability. HAp-modified PLGA scaffolds were found biocompatible and able to sustain both ASCs and MSCs viability over 21 d, as well as functionality both in basal and osteoinductive media conditioning. *In vivo* implantation in a subcutaneous rat model further confirmed biocompatibility of the 3D printed PLGA-HAp [143]. Wattanaanek *et al* recently reported on 3D printing multiple concentrations of amorphous CaP and calcium sulfate hemihydrate (CSH) within alginate and cellulose for bone regeneration [144]. Biocompatibility was tested *in vitro* using MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts, where the groups containing 18% and 20% amorphous CaP/CSH in the biopolymer showed the highest cell proliferation over seven days.

Overall, composites with CaP and biopolymers have been widely explored, and hold great potential in generating 3D printed constructs for bone regeneration.

4.3. Composites with BAGs

BAG can provide additional bioactivity to composite inks depending on the concentration of the ions released upon degradation, figure 3(c). Here, research investigating 3D printable composite inks using BAG for bone regeneration are highlighted.

In early approaches of 3D printing BAG, Bergmann *et al* combined $\text{CaNaPO}_4 + \text{CaSiO}_3$ with β -TCP and a mixture of orthophosphoric acid, pyrophosphoric acid, and isopropanol [145]. Here it was demonstrated that the composite ink was printable and stable in culture, showing remarkable mechanical properties that could be modulated by the ratio of included BAG. Subsequently, the inclusion of BAG to biopolymers was extensively investigated assessing their biological potential to support mineralization *in vitro* and bone regeneration *in vivo*. For example, the study performed by Wang *et al*, where BAG polyphosphate was added to an alginate and gelatin-based hydrogel ink for 3D bioprinting of SaOS-2 cells, enhancing their proliferation and mineralization [146]. Similarly, in a study by Ojansivu *et al*, the biofabrication of 3D printed scaffolds combining BAG (mol% 47.12 SiO_2 , 6.73 B_2O_3 , 6.77 CaO , 22.66 Na_2O , 1.72 P_2O_5 , 5 MgO , 10 SrO) with gelatin, alginate and cellulose nanofibrils was described [147]. This composite ink was successfully bioprinted in combination with SaOs-2 cells and hMSCs, with ALP indicating early osteogenic commitment. Another study by Guduric *et al* included inorganic filler BAG (molar ratio Si:P:Ca of 80:5:15 with Ca substituted by Zn) in an organic matrix of alginate and methylcellulose [148]. This composite biomaterial-ink showed

suitability of bioprinting with hMSCs, revealing a promising bone tissue engineering ink. Also, Leite *et al* reported on the use of alginate dialdehyde-gelatin as biopolymer for the inclusion of BAG (mol% 55 SiO₂, 40 CaO, 5 P₂O₅) [149]. The composite ink allowed for the successful incorporation of MG-63 cells and was further functionalized by the addition of ibuprofen. Cells were homogeneously distributed throughout the composite ink, and no differences were shown in cell viability between hydrogel alone and the composite constructs, indicating that the addition of BAGs did not influence cell viability. Recently, Zhu *et al* reported on 3D printing of alginate dialdehyde-gelatin, but here combined with copper (Cu)-doped mesoporous BAG nanoparticles [150]. The aminated particles introduced cell-adhesive ligands that enabled cell spreading and survival of embedded human osteosarcoma cells (ST2 cells) and mouse MSCs. Scaffolds, without the addition of growth factors, showed *in vitro* enhanced osteogenic differentiation and angiogenesis. This biomaterial-ink shows that the use of BAGs in combination with biopolymers is a promising strategy for bone tissue engineering.

Seeding cells on printed constructs to assess their bioactivity is a common approach. For example, Distler *et al* developed the combination of PLA and 45S5 BAG (wt% 45 SiO₂, 24.5 CaO, 24.5 Na₂O, 6 P₂O₅) as composite ink for EBP [151]. Scaffolds bioactivity and cytocompatibility was assessed *in vitro* using MC3T3E1 pre-osteoblast and hASCs, where gene expression analyses indicated the beneficial impact of including BAG, since these formulations showed increased osteogenic differentiation in comparison to PLA alone. Additionally, Aráoz *et al* used 45S5 BAG (wt% 45 SiO₂, 24.5 CaO, 24.5 Na₂O, 6 P₂O₅) and PHBV to 3D print composite scaffolds with interconnected pores [152]. Scaffolds exhibited similar mechanical and biological properties to those of trabecular bone ECM, with no cytotoxic effects, with enhanced cell spreading when BAG was included in PHBV inks. Saberi *et al* recently demonstrated the 3D printing of scaffolds for bone regeneration consisting of PLA and spray dried glass-ceramic microparticles (SGCMs) [153]. Matrices were shown to have well-defined and interconnected pores and a homogenous distribution of the SGCMs. Further, mechanical testing indicated that the compressive strength depends on the porosity and the presence of SGCMs. *In vitro* evaluation using hMSCs resulted in improved cell adhesion and viability, higher ALP activity, and better mineralization capacity on the composite. Bednarzig *et al* also highlighted the influence of printed porous structures in their 3D printed composite scaffolds using alginate with BAG 13–93 and HAp [154]. Biocompatibility investigations were carried out *in vitro* with the composite ink using MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts. The 3D printed scaffold, with interconnected pores,

showed both indirect and direct increased viability and a high proliferation rate. Furthermore, another study using BAG for bone regeneration was performed by Schätzlein *et al*, where PLA and a varying amount, up to 20%, of osteoconductive S53P4 BAG was combined [155]. Microgrooves, created by 3D printing, serve as a nucleus for cell aggregation resulting *in vitro* in hMSCs adhesion and proliferation and demonstrates the potential for the treatment of critical sized defects. Including *in vivo* evaluation, Ulbrich *et al* introduced niobium containing BAG into poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) biopolymer [156]. *In vitro* analysis using MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts showed higher mineralization on the composite group compared to the PBAT without the BAG. However, *in vivo* evaluation in a rat femur resulted in new bone formation at the defect site, showing that the inclusion of BAG is a promising strategy for bone regeneration.

Other studies have focused on using BAG composite for drug delivery. Wu *et al* showed that the fabrication of mesoporous BAG (80% SiO₂, 16% CaO and 4% P₂O₅) in a sodium alginate and gelatin biopolymer facilitated direct printing of naringin and calcitonin gene-related peptides, which then had sustained release for up to 21 d [157]. In contrast, when the peptides were absorbed on the surface of the printed construct, they were completely released in 48 h. When cultured *in vitro* with MG-63 cells, their proliferation was promoted, and the expression of osteogenesis-related genes was upregulated. In another study by Monavari *et al*, a composite ink was prepared from mesoporous silica-calcium nanoparticles (mol% 70 SiO₂ and 30 CaO) into an alginate dialdehyde-gelatin hydrogel [158]. Scaffolds were functionalized with icariin as natural osteogenic drug. Regardless of incorporation mode, either as loaded into the mesoporous silica-calcium nanoparticles or freely distributed within the hydrogel, scaffolds could hold and deliver icariin efficiently showing enhanced osteoblast proliferation, adhesion, and differentiation. In the study by Wang *et al*, a composite ink consisting of BAG and PCL was used for doxycycline delivery to stimulate BMP-2 expression [159]. Here, the ink was 3D printed together with an C3H10T1/2 cell-laden ink of GelMA and methacrylated hyaluronic acid. Results gathered *in vitro*, using C3H10T1/2 cells, and *in vivo*, subcutaneous in nude mice, revealed active secretion of BMP-2 to significantly promote osteoblast differentiation and bone formation. Recently, Chen *et al* doped BAGs with lithium (Li-BAG) further blending the filler with PLGA to enhance the osteogenic ability in diabetic osteopathy. The synergistic effect of high-glucose environment and Li ions was investigated *in vitro*, demonstrating the ability of Li-BAG to drive osteogenic differentiation of MSCs both in low and high-glucose conditions. The modified BAG combined with PLGA was 3D printed to fabricate a

supporting structure to fill a calvarial defect in diabetes mellitus mice, driving the recruitment of stem cells towards the full repair of critical defects [160].

4.4. Overview and perspectives

When considering 3D printable inorganic-biopolymers composites for bone regeneration, a fundamental distinction should be made between primary and secondary bone healing. Hydrated 3D polymer networks are intrinsically more suited to support secondary fracture healing via an intermediate cartilage template and endochondral bone formation. On the other hand, CaP supports direct bone formation via primary bone healing.

Another important distinction should be made between hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers. Hydrophilic polymers are generally crosslinked into hydrogels and can be used for embedding cells in 3D, figure 4. For cell-laden composites, the inorganic filler increases the shear forces locally experienced by the loaded cells, with negative impact on survival. Hydrophobic polymers such as PCL or other polyesters are generally used to create mechanical competent structures which can be filled with cell-laden hydrogels, or where cells can directly adhere to their surface. In most applications, with thermoplastics such as PCL it is possible to achieve more precise control over porosity and architecture [23]. However, one of the drawbacks of hydrophobic polymers is poor cell adhesion due to ECM proteins being adsorbed in a denatured state unsuitable for cell binding [161]. Cell-laden hydrogels dispensed in a hydrophobic scaffold also display limited migration, thereby hampering the cellularization of inner parts of the scaffold.

The combination of multiple biomaterial-inks has shown promising results and could potentially be helpful in creating cell-laden composite bone graft substitutes. Novel strategies such as hybrid 3D printing platforms have been introduced, further aiding the printability of composite inks by supporting the overall printed structure. For instance, Diloksumpan *et al* combined MEW together with EBP to develop 3D structures [125]. Another example of combining techniques was demonstrated by Wang *et al*, where two biomaterial-inks, with one acellular composite ink and the other a cell-laden biopolymer ink, were combined in 3D printing a bone regenerative scaffold.

Composite biomaterial-inks made of inorganic particles and biopolymers pose 3D printing technical challenges, figure 4. For EBP nozzles with small orifices are necessary to achieve the desired resolution, with diameters typically between 250 and 410 μm , which can easily be obstructed by particle aggregates forming within the cartridge. Filter pressing is an additional risk [162]. This phenomenon consists in phase separation with the liquid phase being preferentially extruded, leaving a phase enriched in inorganic particles behind [163]. Filter pressing can be limited by decreasing particle size, increasing the

viscosity of the liquid phase, or using particles of rounder shape [162]. Besides the above listed challenges, when including inorganic particles in biopolymers the printability can be limited to the particle size. Due to that printability is evaluated in a different manner in reported studies and often the measurements are not quantitative, comparing between different papers is difficult [164].

Nozzle-free biofabrication techniques such as SLA may also involve challenges in using composite inks with inorganic particles, which can settle within the vat or scatter the light, with loss in resolution. Also in this case, a compromise should be found between a viscosity sufficiently high to prevent settling, and sufficiently low for removing the non-cured resin from the object being printed [164].

An additional common aspect in the reported 3D printing of composite inks is the functionalization of scaffolds with growth factors, figure 4 [42, 128, 132, 138, 141]. The inclusion of growth factors in 3D printed composite inks provided temporal control over the incorporated therapeutics and showed controlled release profiles to maximize their efficacy [42, 57, 61, 121, 128, 132, 138, 141]. Thus, inorganic fillers such as silicate nanoparticles have been found capable of sustaining the release of a plethora of growth factors of interest for skeletal regeneration, preventing rapid burst release by the close interaction mediated by both positive and negative charged surfaces of the particulate. Angiogenic factors, such as VEGF, enable vessel formation by promoting endothelial and progenitor cell migration and proliferation [165–167]. Blood vessels are essential in the structural template for bone development, as they supply the fundamental elements for bone homeostasis, such as oxygen, minerals, growth factors and osteogenic progenitor cells that are needed to support the osteogenesis process. Therefore, VEGF has been used in numerous studies to functionalize 3D printed composite inks for the fabrication of functional scaffolds that support osteogenesis [42, 57, 61, 121]. Given its relevance for skeletal differentiation, BMP-2 is also an obvious candidate for inclusion in biomaterial-inks for bone healing [168, 169].

Besides VEGF and BMP-2 a large variety of biological stimuli remains to be investigated in combination with composite biomaterial-inks for bone healing. For example, the importance of neurogenesis in bone regeneration is being increasingly recognized [170, 171]. Bone tissue is both vascularized and innervated and nerve fibres are present throughout the whole bone. Literature has shown a close relationship between nerve fibres with angiogenesis and osteogenesis [172], but has been under investigated in 3D printing of composite constructs for bone regeneration. Thus, new research in the neurovascular interplay shows high potential for therapeutic approaches to enhance bone regeneration by modulating angiogenesis.

Inorganic Fillers	 Bioactive Glasses		
Properties			
Printability	++ 42, 57, 61, 121-124	++ 86, 113, 125-135, 137-144	++ 145-160
Cell inclusion	++ 42, 57, 61, 121-122	+ 127, 129, 133	++ 146-150
Drug delivery	++ 42, 57, 61, 121	++ 128, 132, 138, 141	+ 157-160

Figure 4. Comparison of inorganic fillers used in 3D printing approaches for bone regeneration. Inorganic fillers comprising NSPs, CaP particles and BAGs are compared over the ability of influencing ultimate ink properties, such as printability and the possibility to encapsulate and deliver cells and drugs in 3D.

One further direction for upcoming research lays in harnessing the potential of inorganic fillers and their combination with polymers as functional stimuli of the immune system for driving bone repair. The osteoimmunology field is progressing at increasing pace [173] unveiling how innate and adaptive immunity influence bone regeneration to avoid chronic inflammation and non-union [174]. Increasing efforts are being dedicated to manipulating the interplay between macrophages and MSCs trying to provoke an anti-inflammatory (M2) immune response. Examples of incorporation of immune modulating cytokines, anisotropic structures or CaP in different sizes and morphologies, have shown great promise to promote bone regeneration, however this approach has not been adequately investigated in 3D printed composite bone implants [175, 176].

Personalized 3D printed CaP-based implants are already available as medical devices [177], indicating that similar constructs based on composite scaffolds are realistic. To promote a rapid clinical translation, an advisable strategy would be the exploitation of clinically used materials, such as CaP used in cement putties. Nevertheless, the translational potential of clinically used materials for bioprinting purposes is still at its infancy, holding great potential for the application of inorganic fillers inclusion in clinically used bioinks in the near future. Another obstacle to fast clinical translation is the limited relevance of the currently used *in vivo* models. Recapitulation of the targeted disease is vital when performing experiments *in vivo*, but this is often neglected with the result that most studies fail to identify the specific clinical indication they are targeting and the justification for choosing one animal model over another. *In vivo* models cannot fully recreate the targeted human

disease, however the quality of the experimental data should be maximized to increase the clinical translation potential of the developed scaffolds [178].

Overall, although a lot of work has been done on 3D printing composite structures for bone healing, a lot remains to be understood to develop 3D printed implants that can replace autologous bone transplantation.

5. Conclusion

The clinical demands in the field of bone repair still present major challenges. A 3D printing has emerged as a promising technology that facilitates both spatial control over scaffold architecture to anatomically match complicated bone defect sites, and temporal control over the incorporated therapeutics to maximize their efficacy. Additionally, this technology enables the fabrication of composite scaffolds to resemble the heterogenous composition of bone, consisting of inorganic salts and organic matrix. This review highlights biofabrication methods of composite biomaterial-inks, incorporating inorganic fillers, such as NSPs, CaP, and BAG, combined with biopolymers, including alginate, gelatin and PCL. Ultimately, the inclusion of inorganic fillers into soft biopolymers has led to enhanced bioactivity and printability of composite biomaterial-inks, while enabling the tuning of their mechanical properties. However, challenges remain, including clogging of the printer nozzle and filter pressing, thus impeding the high throughput fabrication of scaffolds. Furthermore, composite scaffolds have been used to locally deliver growth factors with controlled release profiles to maximize their efficacy and enhance bone regeneration. Moreover, the possibility to include cells into

composite inks has been investigated but has been largely limited by the high content of inorganic filler. Only further research will burgeon further developments of 3D printed composite implants towards satisfying the increasing clinical demands in bone healing.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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